

Institutionalizing Family Entrepreneurship Functions in the Renewed Uzbekistan

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 30 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 03 Nov 2024; **Published:** 03 Dec 2024

Abstract: The article examines the rules and mechanisms of institutional conditions for the formation of entrepreneurial activity, the obligation of family businesses to comply with these established rules and norms, the target group of reforms being implemented in small and private businesses in Uzbekistan, and most importantly, the development of family entrepreneurship, which is one of the tasks set for the further development and liberalization of the Uzbek economy and does not fall within the scope of the studied problems of sociologists, psychologists, cultural studies and political scientists within the framework of general philosophical and socio-philosophical.

Keywords: social groups, institutional, family entrepreneurship, small and private business, progress, Action Strategy, socio-humanitarian, general philosophical analysis, expertise.

Introduction. The events that took place in Uzbekistan in the last decade of the last century not only led to drastic changes in the political and economic spheres, but also affected the social component of our society. New social groups appeared, a social layer of entrepreneurs was formed. All these changes were reflected in the Uzbek model of progress described by the first president of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov. The institution of private property was restored in the country. Such changes contribute to the emergence of new types of entrepreneurship, one of which is family entrepreneurship a type of business in which all or several members of the family participate. The institutional conditions for the formation of entrepreneurial activity were taken as a set of rules and mechanisms. In this, family business entities are obliged to comply with these established rules and norms. Even a small change in institutional structure dynamics affects the entrepreneurial structure [1]. Special guarantees are mandatory elements of institutional conditions in the formation of entrepreneurial activity.

In modern Uzbekistan, a radical macroeconomic restructuring is underway, aimed at implementing the transition to an open, socially oriented market economy. In this regard, changes in the structure of the business are taking place under the influence of resource, structure and institutional factors. The development of family entrepreneurship is aimed at strengthening family ties in one cell of society and improving the economic situation in a particular region. The activities of a separate family enterprise help not only to profit, but also to increase the cohesion of members of the same family within the framework of close cooperation both at home and at work.

The target group of reforms carried out in Uzbekistan in small and private business and,

most importantly, is considered as the driving force for the changes taking place in the socio-economic and sociopolitical environment. Currently, entrepreneurial activity is carried out through market infrastructure institutions consisting of a complex of interconnected project - technological, information and organizational systems of production [2]. This infrastructure makes it possible to carry out the processes that take place from the full cycle of entrepreneurship - an idea, until its implementation in the form of a particular good or service. In order for the institutional system of entrepreneurship to be successfully implemented, it must have a regulatory framework that has a positive impact and an effective system aimed at bringing the products of the enterprise to the market [3]. From this it follows that the formation of institutional infrastructure is considered the most serious and urgent issue.

The goal of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan is progress, that is, progress. Progress is understood as a special form of institutional and socio - cultural change that leads society towards modernization. Modernization, on the other hand, leads to the liberalization of the political sphere, the differentiation and complication of ownership relations, the change in the lifestyle of the population, the growth of the pace of development. In a certain sense, progress is a response to the " call of history", to dynamism in the country and the world, to the complication of problems.

The role of institutions is to provide family entrepreneurs with the best opportunities for the creation of new enterprises, as well as to create laughing conditions for its functioning and development in the future. The institutional mukhit establishes the rules of the game, understandable to all economic entities, and forms the conditions and incentives that will be necessary for entrepreneurial activity. The institutional environment has a significant impact on the aspiration, speed and character of entrepreneurial activity of shakhas, directly and indirectly affecting their behavior [4].

According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the family has the right to be the main branch of society and the protection of society and the state. Therefore, the development of the family in Uzbekistan at a global level within the framework of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals [5]. one of the main factors in ensuring the socio-economic development of the country has been identified as an important direction for the development of family entrepreneurship. Consequently, family entrepreneurship is considered by the UN and the International Labor Organization as one of the strategic directions in the fight against poverty.

A.Akhmediev, U. Valijanov, O. Ismailov, L. Ishmukhamedov, S.Salaev, I.Tursunov, E.Ergashev, M.The dissertation work of Eshov and others is directly devoted to the issues of the development of entrepreneurship in new institutional conditions. Their work focuses on the godly or sectoral aspects of solving this problem [6].

It is known that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev began his work as the head of the public administration system and in 2017-2021 adopted the action strategy of further development of Uzbekistan, the tasks of "regularly improving the solid legislative and legal framework for the development of the industry, granting benefits and preferences for family entrepreneurship, providing technical and technological re-equipment of production and systematically providing assistance.

In the strategy of action [8] the development of family entrepreneurship is considered to have a special place among the priority tasks set for the further development and liberalization of the economy of Uzbekistan. Because, the contribution of family entrepreneurship to the sustainable development of the economy of our country and the provision of employment is high. At the same time, the level of family well-being and quality of life is considered to largely depend on the income from family entrepreneurial activities.

Based on this document, in order to create conditions for each family to engage in entrepreneurship and have a stable source of income, it is necessary to radically improve the material conditions of the population, ensure the implementation of significant positive changes in the quality and level of lifestyle;

ensuring comprehensive support of entrepreneurial initiatives of the population, systematic practical assistance in the organization and implementation of entrepreneurial activities;

teaching the population entrepreneurial skills and providing practical assistance to organize the appropriate type of activity; to provide additional jobs and the opportunity to earn income;

to establish mini-clusters in families who have already begun to engage in new business activities in the neighborhoods;

the construction of market infrastructure facilities, service and service stations and other measures are being implemented [9].

Family entrepreneurial activity is largely determined by the nature of the entrepreneur himself, family members and the business entities in which they are engaged in organizing it. However, experience shows that the nature of entrepreneurship, the stable individual and personal characteristics of the entities that make it up, is characterized by the integralization of relationships formed on the basis of the benefits that a person receives from the biosomatic, genetic, natural environment, their temperament, inclinations and collective income.

Therefore, in theory, when taking social and humanitarian Sciences, special attention is paid to the national, social and individual character of family entrepreneurship.

The main components that have an important impact on the formation of family entrepreneurship according to the assumptions carried out within the framework of modern socio-humanitarian knowledge are the natural, bio somatic and genetic determinations of Man, which form the natural basis of entrepreneurship, socio-psychological and socio-cultural determinations that have a significant impact on the National Character, mentality and the system, his vital positivity and measure of harmony with the outside world are the dominant component of personal self-interest.

And within the framework of general philosophical and socio-philosophical knowledge, it falls into the framework of the studied problems of sociologists, psychologists, economists, cultural scientists and political scientists, with the inconsistency of the specifics of business or family entrepreneurial ethics.

When the problem of family entrepreneurship is placed on the agenda, it is first necessary to shed light on the essence of the philosophical analysis between the family and society, as well as to study such pressing issues as the paradigm of interest in the balanced relationship between the entrepreneur and society as retrospection (an economic, socio-philosophical analysis of its value in the historical genesis of the family and its significance for the development of the entrepreneur) and family interest.

Therefore, in the context of modern Uzbekistan undergoing a transformation, a complex of issues related to family business and family entrepreneurship in the field of social and humanitarian sciences is particularly relevant in the new system of socio-economic and spiritual relations.

The success of family business development is determined not only by external institutional conditions, where there is a clear positive dynamic in the Uzbek economy, but also by the level of quality of the management system within the enterprise. At the same time, it is very important for family businesses to create employees based on a management system that

allows them to achieve appropriate work discipline, but does not interfere with family relationships in business relationships [11,12].

It is very important to build a management system at a family enterprise, to clearly define the responsibility of each of them, to preserve certain freedom and independence, both in cases where the husband manages the work of the spouse and in cases where the father manages the work of the adult children.

It should be noted that the difficulties in the former system further exacerbated many problems of the family in the country, regardless of the family as the most important component of society, family problems were treated indifferently. As a result, society and the state pursued a policy against private property and entrepreneurship. Such a policy led to the devaluation of the value and interests of the family. The announcement in society that "private property is a tool for human exploitation" blocked the path of private property, business, and entrepreneurship.

Today, under the influence of changes in politics, economics, and culture, relationships within the social structure, relationships between various social institutions, including society and the institution of the family, have changed. Thus, family entrepreneurship, as the most important social condition for nationwide modernization at all levels, began to form one of the important aspects of the mechanisms of change in society based on the interests of the individual (entrepreneur, businessman) [13,14,15].

At the same time, the reduction of the state's role and participation in the republic's economy, the widespread introduction of market principles and mechanisms into the management of economic sectors, as well as the implementation of targeted measures to improve the well-being and standard of living of the population, have also shaped a mechanism aimed at establishing full-fledged partnerships with small businesses and family businesses in the country [16,17,18].

It should be noted that family business is the most widespread form of entrepreneurial activity in the world and relies on centuries-old traditions. In countries with a developed market economy, family firms form the foundation of societal well-being and development, and they account for a significant portion of the goods produced and services provided. The middle class, formed on this basis, is the foundation of social and political stability in society.

Analysis of foreign experience shows that the importance and role of family entrepreneurship play an important role in economic reform and ensuring a high level of income for the population.

In particular, it was noted that in recent years, the content and essence of political, social, and economic relations, the image of our society have completely changed, these positive changes are reflected in the lives of our compatriots, it is important to convey to our country and the international community the work done to raise the standard of living, conscious thinking, knowledge and culture of our people through clear evidence and examples, deep scientific analysis and expert assessments.

It should be noted that today, in the context of a renewed Uzbekistan, a new stage of the process of family entrepreneurship and its development is emerging. The implementation of this activity will contribute not only to the development of the family in the future, but also to the development of the country. Family entrepreneurship is the foundation of entrepreneurial activity carried out by family members at their own risk and with the aim of generating income (profit) under their own property liability.

Therefore, the establishment of family entrepreneurship as one of the ways to achieve prosperity in the republic, its popular nature, creates the opportunity to address the most important socio-economic issues, namely ensuring the well-being of families and citizens

and employment. Therefore, the development of family entrepreneurship is becoming a vital necessity for our country, and the development of the industry has always been in the focus of the republic's government.

This dissertation research, to a certain extent, serves to fulfill the tasks outlined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Family Entrepreneurship" of April 26, 2012, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-4725 of May 15, 2015, "On Measures to Eliminate Obstacles to Ensuring Reliable Protection of Private Property, Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship, Accelerated Development of Private Property and Improve the Quality of Work," the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4, This dissertation research, to a certain extent, serves to fulfill the tasks outlined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-3777 of June 7, 2018, "On the Implementation of the "Every Family - Entrepreneur" Program," the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 631 of August 7, 2018, "On the Organization of the Activities of Family Guest Houses," as well as other regulatory documents adopted in this area.

These documents put forward urgent tasks to provide comprehensive assistance to the population in engaging in certain types of work aimed at obtaining income, the development of family entrepreneurship, and the systematic organization of work in this direction. It provides for the financing of projects and activities within the framework of the "Every Family is an Entrepreneur" program at the expense of the Fund for Reconstruction and Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and credit lines of international financial institutions.

Speaking about the implementation of the program "Every family is an entrepreneur," President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "One or two factories cannot provide one percent of the population with work. Here, people can be fed only through entrepreneurship and craftsmanship. If we invest in households, provide them with the necessary equipment, teach them how to work intelligently, people will support themselves.

They buy things for their home, buy books for their children, pay taxes, electricity, and go into the budget. In a year, the money we have spent will be doubled. This is how the economic mechanism should be.

The importance and role of family entrepreneurship in the country's economic development is very important. Although the work done in this area is yielding its effectiveness in the modernizing Uzbekistan, there is still much work to be done in this area. The reason for this is the relatively high unemployment rate in Uzbekistan, with a population of about 36 million people. For this reason, a certain number of workers leave the country and raise families as labor migrants in the far and near abroad. According to official data, the unemployment rate among the economically active population in the first half of the year exceeded 7 percent. Here, it is necessary to pay attention to the difference between the economically active population (16.6 million) and the economically inactive population (5.2 million). It is no coincidence that the government has put the issue of developing family entrepreneurship on the agenda as a significant solution to this situation.

Through the development of family entrepreneurship, the country will ensure employment for the population, expand their sources of income, accelerate adaptation skills to modern requirements of the market economy, increase the number of taxpayers, and ensure the working, physical, and moral maturity of the younger generation.

One of the characteristics of family entrepreneurship is that the experience accumulated in it is of great importance in the phased expansion of the scope of entrepreneurship and the creation of competitive production enterprises on this basis.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the aforementioned legal foundations for organizing

family business and family entrepreneurship and the state policy implemented in this area will contribute to further increasing the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country's economy, ensuring employment for the population and further increasing their income, increasing the number of representatives of the middle class among the population.

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